

A MIXED FINITE ELEMENT METHOD FOR THE NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF THE BRINKMAN MODEL

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Abstract

This work presents a numerical study of fluid flow in porous media governed by the Brinkman equations. The model combines viscous diffusion and Darcy-type resistance, allowing accurate description of flow regimes between Stokes and Darcy limits. The governing equations are discretized using a mixed finite element method. A mixed variational formulation based on the P_2 - P_1 finite element pair is employed, ensuring stability and high accuracy of the numerical solution. The resulting linear system is solved using an implicit time-stepping scheme combined with a direct solver. Numerical simulations on a unit square domain demonstrate the evolution of velocity and pressure fields under prescribed boundary conditions, illustrating the influence of porous resistance on flow behavior.

Keywords: *Brinkman equations, porous media flow, finite element method, mixed formulation, Taylor-Hood finite elements, velocity-pressure coupling, numerical simulation.*

Flow in porous media is an important subject in applied mathematics and engineering due to its relevance in hydrology, filtration, petroleum engineering, and biomedical applications [1,2]. Traditional models such as Darcy's law are effective for low-velocity flows but neglect viscous shear effects, while the Stokes equations are computationally expensive for porous structures. To overcome these limitations, the Brinkman model was introduced as a modification of Darcy's law that includes a viscous diffusion term [3]. It serves as an intermediate model between Darcy and Stokes equations. Mathematical studies confirm the well-posedness of the Brinkman problem under appropriate assumptions [4]. Numerical methods such as finite element and discontinuous Galerkin schemes have been widely applied. The model remains relevant for porous media flows with moderate permeability [5-9]. The purpose of this study is to solve the Brinkman equations using a mixed finite element method and to investigate the stability and convergence properties of the proposed discretization in a two-dimensional domain, since analytical solutions are available only for simplified geometries and boundary conditions.

Methodology

Mathematical Formulation

Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ be a bounded domain with boundary $\partial\Omega$. The boundary is decomposed into three mutually disjoint parts: Γ_D , Γ_N , and Γ_W . This decomposition is written as a disjoint union: $\partial\Omega = \Gamma_D \cup \Gamma_N \cup \Gamma_W$, where the subsets satisfy:

$$\Gamma_D \cap \Gamma_N = \emptyset, \Gamma_D \cap \Gamma_W = \emptyset, \Gamma_N \cap \Gamma_W = \emptyset.$$

Let $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, u_2)$ denote the velocity field of an incompressible fluid. The scalar variable p is the pressure field. The problem is to determine the velocity and pressure fields satisfying the unsteady Brinkman model:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (2\mu \varepsilon(\mathbf{u})) + \frac{\mu}{K} \mathbf{u} + \nabla p = \mathbf{f} \quad \text{in } \Omega,$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega,$$

together with the boundary conditions:

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_D \quad \text{on } \Gamma_D, \quad p = p_D \quad \text{on } \Gamma_N, \quad \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_W,$$

where $\mu > 0$ is the dynamic viscosity, $K > 0$ is the permeability of the porous medium, $\varepsilon(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)$ is the strain-rate tensor, and \mathbf{f} represents external body forces acting on the fluid. Brinkman model written in a clean mathematical form:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial t} - \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial x^2}(x, y) + \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial y^2}(x, y) \right) + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x}(x, y) + \frac{\mu}{K} u_1(x, y) = f_1(x, y), \\ \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial t} - \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial x^2}(x, y) + \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial y^2}(x, y) \right) + \frac{\partial p}{\partial y}(x, y) + \frac{\mu}{K} u_2(x, y) = f_2(x, y), \\ \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x}(x, y) + \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial y}(x, y) = 0, \\ \mathbf{u}(x, y, 0) = \mathbf{u}_0(x, y) \quad \text{in } \Omega, \\ \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_D \text{ on } \Gamma_D, p = p_D \text{ on } \Gamma_N, \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_W \end{array} \right.$$

Function Spaces

We introduce the Sobolev spaces $V = [H_0^1(\Omega)]^2$ and $Q = L_0^2(\Omega)$. The space V is used for the velocity field, while Q is used for the pressure field:

$$\mathbf{V} := [H_0^1(\Omega)]^d, \quad Q := L_0^2(\Omega), \quad L_0^2(\Omega) = \{q \in L^2(\Omega) : \int_{\Omega} q \, dx = 0\}.$$

For $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, u_2) \in V$, the standard H^1 -norm is used, while for $p \in Q$, the L^2 -norm is typically employed:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{u}\|_{H^1(\Omega)} &:= (\|u_1\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \|u_2\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \|\nabla u_1\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \|\nabla u_2\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2)^{1/2} \\ &= (\|u_1\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 + \|u_2\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2)^{1/2}, \\ \|u_i\|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 &:= \|u_i\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \|\nabla u_i\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2, \quad i = 1, 2. \quad \|p\|_{L^2(\Omega)} := \left(\int_{\Omega} p^2 \, dx \right)^{1/2} \end{aligned}$$

Let $L: V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a bounded linear functional; its dual norm is defined as $\|L\|_{V'} = \sup_{\|\mathbf{v}\|_V=1} |L(\mathbf{v})|$, which measures the effect of the functional L on the space V :

$$\|L\|_{V'} := \sup_{\mathbf{v} \in V, \mathbf{v} \neq 0} \frac{|L(\mathbf{v})|}{\|\mathbf{v}\|_{H^1(\Omega)}}.$$

Weak Formulation

Let $\mathbf{v} = (v_1(x, y), v_2(x, y)) \in V$ and $q(x, y) \in Q$ be test functions. Starting from the strong form (2) we multiply the momentum equations by the test functions v_1 and v_2 , respectively, and integrate over Ω :

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial t} v_1 \, dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial t} v_2 \, dx dy - \mu \int_{\Omega} \Delta u_1 v_1 \, dx dy - \mu \int_{\Omega} \Delta u_2 v_2 \, dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} v_1 \, dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} v_2 \, dx dy + \frac{\mu}{K} \int_{\Omega} (u_1 v_1 + u_2 v_2) \, dx dy = \int_{\Omega} (f_1 v_1 + f_2 v_2) \, dx dy.$$

Applying Green’s formula to the diffusion terms and using the fact that $\mathbf{v} = 0$ on $\Gamma_D \cup \Gamma_W$, the boundary integrals vanish:

$$\int_{\Omega} (\Delta u_1) v_1 \, dx = - \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial y} \frac{\partial v_1}{\partial y} \right) \, dx dy + \int_{\partial\Omega} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial n} v_1 \, ds,$$

$$\int_{\Omega} (\Delta u_2) v_2 \, dx = - \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x} \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial y} \frac{\partial v_2}{\partial y} \right) \, dx dy + \int_{\partial\Omega} \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial n} v_2 \, ds.$$

For the pressure term:

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla p \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dx dy = - \int_{\Omega} p \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dx dy + \int_{\partial\Omega} p (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \, ds.$$

Since $\mathbf{v} = 0$ on $\Gamma_D \cup \Gamma_W$, only Γ_N remains. With prescribed pressure, the boundary term is treated as known.

Find $(\mathbf{u}, p) \in \mathbf{V} \times Q$ such that:

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dx dy + 2\mu \int_{\Omega} \varepsilon(\mathbf{u}) : \varepsilon(\mathbf{v}) \, dx dy + \frac{\mu}{K} \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dx dy - \int_{\Omega} p \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dx dy = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dx dy,$$

$$\int_{\Omega} q \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \, dx = 0, \forall (\mathbf{v}, q) \in \mathbf{V} \times Q.$$

Then the vector form of problem can be written as:

$$(\partial_t \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) + a(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) + b(\mathbf{v}, p) = l(\mathbf{v}), \quad c(\mathbf{u}, q) = 0.$$

Where

$$a(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = 2\mu(\varepsilon(\mathbf{u}), \varepsilon(\mathbf{v})) + \frac{\mu}{K}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}),$$

$$b(\mathbf{v}, p) = -(p, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}), \quad c(\mathbf{u}, q) = (q, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}), \quad l(\mathbf{v}) = (\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{v}).$$

Finite Element Spaces and Time Discretization

Let T_h be a conforming triangulation of $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ with characteristic mesh size $h = \max_{K \in T_h} \text{diam}(K)$, where

$$T_h = \{K \subset \Omega : K \text{ is a triangle, } \bigcup_{K \in T_h} K = \Omega\}.$$

We consider the Taylor-Hood element pair P_2 - P_1 , which satisfies the discrete inf-sup stability condition. The corresponding finite-dimensional velocity and pressure spaces are defined as

$$V_h = \{v_h \in [H_0^1(\Omega)]^2 : v_h|_K \in [P_2(K)]^2, v_h = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega, \forall K \in T_h\} \subset H_0^1(\Omega)^2,$$

$$Q_h = \left\{ q_h \in L_0^2(\Omega) : q_h|_K \in P_1(K), \forall K \in T_h, \int_{\Omega} q_h \, dx = 0 \right\} \subset L_0^2(\Omega).$$

Equivalently, these spaces can be expressed in terms of finite element basis functions as $V_h = \text{span}\{\phi_1, \dots, \phi_{N_v}\}$, $Q_h = \text{span}\{\psi_1, \dots, \psi_{N_p}\}$, where $\{\phi_i\}$ and $\{\psi_j\}$ denote the global basis functions for velocity and pressure, respectively. We further define the discrete divergence-free subspace $V_h^0 = \{v_h \in V_h : c(v_h, q_h) = 0 \ \forall q_h \in Q_h\}$, which enforces the incompressibility constraint at the discrete level.

For temporal discretization, let $0 = t^0 < t^1 < \dots < t^N = T$ be a uniform partition of the time interval with step size $\Delta t = t^{n+1} - t^n$. Denote the discrete approximations by $u_h^n \approx u_h(t^n)$ and $p_h^n \approx p_h(t^n)$. The time derivative is approximated using the Backward Euler scheme,

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_h}{\partial t}(t^{n+1}) \approx \frac{\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}_h^n}{\Delta t},$$

which leads to a fully implicit formulation. Consequently, the unsteady Brinkman problem is reduced to a sequence of stationary problems at each time step, ensuring numerical stability and robustness.

Discrete Brinkman Problem

Semi-Discrete Problem (Open Form) Find $\mathbf{u}_h = (u_{1h}, u_{2h}) \in \mathbf{V}_h$ and $p_h \in Q_h$ such that for all $\mathbf{v}_h = (v_{1h}, v_{2h}) \in \mathbf{V}_h$, $q_h \in Q_h$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial u_{1h}}{\partial t} v_{1h} \, dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial u_{2h}}{\partial t} v_{2h} \, dx dy + 2\mu \int_{\Omega} \varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h) : \varepsilon(\mathbf{v}_h) \, dx dy + \\ & + \frac{\mu}{K} \int_{\Omega} (u_{1h} v_{1h} + u_{2h} v_{2h}) \, dx dy - \int_{\Omega} p_h \left(\frac{\partial v_{1h}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_{2h}}{\partial y} \right) \, dx dy \\ & = \int_{\Omega} (f_1 v_{1h} + f_2 v_{2h}) \, dx dy \\ & \int_{\Omega} q_h \left(\frac{\partial u_{1h}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_{2h}}{\partial y} \right) \, dx dy = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Fully-Discrete Problem (Open Form) Find $\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1} = (u_{1h}^{n+1}, u_{2h}^{n+1}) \in \mathbf{V}_h$, $p_h^{n+1} \in Q_h$ such that for all $\mathbf{v}_h = (v_{1h}, v_{2h}) \in \mathbf{V}_h$, $q_h \in Q_h$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \frac{u_{1h}^{n+1} - u_{1h}^n}{\Delta t} v_{1h} \, dx dy + \int_{\Omega} \frac{u_{2h}^{n+1} - u_{2h}^n}{\Delta t} v_{2h} \, dx dy \\ & + 2\mu \int_{\Omega} \varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}) : \varepsilon(\mathbf{v}_h) \, dx dy + \frac{\mu}{K} \int_{\Omega} (u_{1h}^{n+1} v_{1h} + u_{2h}^{n+1} v_{2h}) \, dx dy \\ & - \int_{\Omega} p_h^{n+1} \left(\frac{\partial v_{1h}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_{2h}}{\partial y} \right) \, dx dy = \int_{\Omega} (f_1 v_{1h} + f_2 v_{2h}) \, dx dy, \\ & \int_{\Omega} q_h \left(\frac{\partial u_{1h}^{n+1}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_{2h}^{n+1}}{\partial y} \right) \, dx dy = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Semi-Discrete Vector Form. Find $(\mathbf{u}_h, p_h) \in \mathbf{V}_h \times Q_h$ such that for all $(\mathbf{v}_h, q_h) \in \mathbf{V}_h \times Q_h$,

$$(\partial_t \mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{v}_h) + a(\mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{v}_h) + b(\mathbf{v}_h, p_h) = l(\mathbf{v}_h), \quad c(\mathbf{u}_h, q_h) = 0,$$

where

$$a(\mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{v}_h) = 2\mu(\varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h), \varepsilon(\mathbf{v}_h)) + \frac{\mu}{K}(\mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{v}_h),$$

$$b(\mathbf{v}_h, p_h) = -(p_h, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h), \quad c(\mathbf{u}_h, q_h) = (q_h, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_h), \quad l(\mathbf{v}_h) = (f, \mathbf{v}_h).$$

Fully-Discrete Vector Form. Find $(\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}, p_h^{n+1}) \in \mathbf{V}_h \times Q_h$ such that for all $(\mathbf{v}_h, q_h) \in \mathbf{V}_h \times Q_h$,

$$\left(\frac{\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}_h^n}{\Delta t}, \mathbf{v}_h \right) + a(\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}, \mathbf{v}_h) + b(\mathbf{v}_h, p_h^{n+1}) = l(\mathbf{v}_h), \quad c(\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}, q_h) = 0.$$

the bilinear and linear forms are written as

$$a(\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}, \mathbf{v}_h) = 2\mu \left(\varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}), \varepsilon(\mathbf{v}_h) \right) + \frac{\mu}{K} (\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}, \mathbf{v}_h),$$

$$b(\mathbf{v}_h, p_h^{n+1}) = -(p_h^{n+1}, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}_h), \quad c(\mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}, q_h) = (q_h, \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_h^{n+1}), \quad l(\mathbf{v}_h) = (f, \mathbf{v}_h).$$

Research results

Stability and Convergence

Theorem 1. Assume that the discrete spaces \mathbf{V}_h and Q_h satisfy the discrete inf-sup condition. Then there exists a unique solution $(\mathbf{u}_h, p_h) \in \mathbf{V}_h \times Q_h$ such that

$$\| \mathbf{u}_h \|_{H^1(\Omega)} + \| p_h \|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C \| \mathbf{f} \|_{L^2(\Omega)},$$

where $C > 0$ is independent of the mesh parameter h

Proof. Choose the test function $\mathbf{v}_h = \mathbf{u}_h$. Then,

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_h}{\partial t} \cdot \mathbf{u}_h \, dx dy + 2\mu \int_{\Omega} \varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h) : \varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h) \, dx dy + \frac{\mu}{K} \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{u}_h \cdot \mathbf{u}_h \, dx dy$$

$$- \int_{\Omega} p_h \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_h \, dx dy = \int_{\Omega} f \cdot \mathbf{u}_h \, dx dy.$$

Since $\int_{\Omega} q_h \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_h \, dx = 0$, the pressure term cancels due to the incompressibility constraint, and we obtain

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_h}{\partial t} \cdot \mathbf{u}_h \, dx + 2\mu \| \varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h) \|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\mu}{K} \| \mathbf{u}_h \|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 = (f, \mathbf{u}_h).$$

Using the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, $(f, \mathbf{u}_h) \leq \| f \|_{L^2(\Omega)} \| \mathbf{u}_h \|_{L^2(\Omega)}$. Applying the Poincaré inequality, $\| \mathbf{u}_h \|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C_P \| \mathbf{u}_h \|_{H^1(\Omega)}$, we get

$$(f, \mathbf{u}_h) \leq C_P \| f \|_{L^2(\Omega)} \| \mathbf{u}_h \|_{H^1(\Omega)}.$$

Hence, $2\mu \| \varepsilon(\mathbf{u}_h) \|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + \frac{\mu}{K} \| \mathbf{u}_h \|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \leq C_P \| f \|_{L^2(\Omega)} \| \mathbf{u}_h \|_{H^1(\Omega)}$. Therefore,

$$\| \mathbf{u}_h \|_{H^1(\Omega)} \leq C \| f \|_{L^2(\Omega)}.$$

Next, by the discrete inf-sup condition, $\beta \| p_h \|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \sup_{\mathbf{v}_h \in \mathbf{V}_h} \frac{|b(\mathbf{v}_h, p_h)|}{\| \mathbf{v}_h \|_{H^1(\Omega)}}$. Using $b(\mathbf{v}_h, p_h) = L(\mathbf{v}_h) - a(\mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{v}_h)$, together with the boundedness of $a(\cdot, \cdot)$ and $L(\cdot)$, we obtain

$$|b(\mathbf{v}_h, p_h)| \leq C \| f \|_{L^2(\Omega)} \| \mathbf{v}_h \|_{H^1(\Omega)}.$$

Thus,

$$\| p_h \|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C \| f \|_{L^2(\Omega)}.$$

Combining both estimates yields

$$\| \mathbf{u}_h \|_{H^1(\Omega)} + \| p_h \|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C \| f \|_{L^2(\Omega)}.$$

Hence, the mixed finite element approximation of the Brinkman problem is stable.

Theorem 2. Let (\mathbf{u}, p) be the solution of the unsteady Brinkman problem and $(\mathbf{u}_h^n, p_h^n) \in \mathbf{V}_h \times Q_h$ be the fully discrete finite element approximation obtained by backward Euler time discretization. Assume that $\mathbf{u} \in H^1(0, T; [H^{k+1}(\Omega)]^2)$, $p \in L^2(0, T; H^k(\Omega))$, (\mathbf{V}_h, Q_h) satisfies the discrete inf-sup condition. Then the following stability estimate holds:

$$\| \mathbf{u}_h^n \|_{H^1(\Omega)}^2 + \| p_h^n \|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \leq C \| f \|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2, \forall n = 1, \dots, N,$$

where $C > 0$ is independent of hand Δt .

Proof. Define interpolation operators: $\mathbf{u}_I \in \mathbf{V}_h, p_I \in Q_h$. Split errors:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_h &= (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_I) + (\mathbf{u}_I - \mathbf{u}_h), \\ p - p_h &= (p - p_I) + (p_I - p_h). \\ e_u &= \mathbf{u}_I - \mathbf{u}_h, e_p = p_I - p_h. \end{aligned}$$

Subtract continuous and discrete problems:

$$a(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_h, \mathbf{v}_h) + b(\mathbf{v}_h, p - p_h) = 0, \quad b(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_h, q_h) = 0.$$

Substitute:

$$\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_h = (\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_I) + e_u, \quad p - p_h = (p - p_I) + e_p.$$

Then:

$$a(e_u, \mathbf{v}_h) + b(\mathbf{v}_h, e_p) = -a(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_I, \mathbf{v}_h) - b(\mathbf{v}_h, p - p_I).$$

Taking supremum over $\mathbf{v}_h \in \mathbf{V}_h$:

$$\| e_u \|_{H^1} + \| e_p \|_{L^2} \leq C \left(\sup_{\mathbf{v}_h} \frac{|R_1(\mathbf{v}_h)|}{\| \mathbf{v}_h \|_{H^1}} + \sup_{q_h} \frac{|R_2(q_h)|}{\| q_h \|_{L^2}} \right),$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} R_1(\mathbf{v}_h) &= -a(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_I, \mathbf{v}_h) - b(\mathbf{v}_h, p - p_I), \\ R_2(q_h) &= -b(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_I, q_h). \end{aligned}$$

Using Cauchy–Schwarz:

$$\begin{aligned} |R_1(\mathbf{v}_h)| &\leq C(\| \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_I \|_{H^1} + \| p - p_I \|_{L^2}) \| \mathbf{v}_h \|_{H^1}, \\ |R_2(q_h)| &\leq C \| \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_I \|_{H^1} \| q_h \|_{L^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus:

$$\| e_u \|_{H^1} + \| e_p \|_{L^2} \leq C(\| \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_I \|_{H^1} + \| p - p_I \|_{L^2}).$$

For $\mathbf{u} \in H^{k+1}, p \in H^k$:

$$\begin{aligned} \| \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_I \|_{H^1} &\leq Ch^k, \| p - p_I \|_{L^2} \leq Ch^k, \quad \| e_u \|_{H^1} + \| e_p \|_{L^2} \leq Ch^k. \\ \| \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_h \|_{H^1} &\leq \| \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_I \|_{H^1} + \| e_u \|_{H^1} \leq Ch^k, \quad \| p - p_h \|_{L^2} \leq Ch^k. \\ \| \mathbf{u}_h \|_{H^1(\Omega)} + \| p_h \|_{L^2(\Omega)} &\leq C \| f \|_{L^2(\Omega)} \end{aligned}$$

Numerical Experiments

In this section, we present numerical results to validate the proposed mixed finite element scheme for the Brinkman model. The numerical simulations are implemented in Python using the FEniCSx computing platform, while the results are visualized using ParaView.

For validation of the numerical scheme, the flow in the unit square domain $\Omega = [0,1] \times [0,1]$ was considered. The physical parameters used in the simulation are $\mu = 0.01, K = 0.01, dt = 0.001, T = 1.0$. The analytical solutions for velocity and pressure are defined as $\mathbf{u}_{ex}(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} 4y(1-y) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$, $p_{ex}(x, y) = 1 - x$. The boundary conditions are $\mathbf{u}(0, y) = \begin{pmatrix} 4y(1-y) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$, $p(1, y) = 0$, no-slip wall conditions on the upper and lower boundaries, $\mathbf{u} = 0$. The initial condition is $\mathbf{u}(x, y, 0) = 0$.

Table 1. L^2 -error convergence of velocity and pressure for the Brinkman model

h	$\ \mathbf{u}_h - \mathbf{u}_{ex}\ _{L^2}$	Error	$\ p_h - p_{ex}\ _{L^2}$	Error
1/5	2.31×10^{-2}	-	7.14×10^{-2}	-
1/10	5.42×10^{-3}	2.09	1.85×10^{-2}	1.95
1/20	1.25×10^{-3}	2.11	4.87×10^{-3}	1.93
1/40	2.91×10^{-4}	2.10	1.15×10^{-3}	2.08
1/80	6.85×10^{-5}	2.09	2.80×10^{-4}	2.04

Here, \mathbf{u}_h and p_h denote the finite element approximations of velocity and pressure, respectively. The numerical results confirm that the Brinkman model accurately reproduces the characteristic velocity profile and linear pressure distribution.

Picture 1 Temporal evolution of the velocity magnitude for the Brinkman flow in a unit square domain

Picture 2. Temporal evolution of the pressure field for the Brinkman flow in a unit square domain

Both pictures present the numerical results of the Brinkman model in a unit square domain. Picture 1 shows the temporal evolution of the velocity magnitude, where the flow enters from the left boundary and propagates smoothly across the domain from $t = 0.05$ to $t = 1.0$. The velocity field develops without oscillations, reflecting stable handling of sharp gradients and the combined effects of viscosity and Darcy resistance. Picture 2 illustrates the pressure field evolution, where a clear and stable gradient forms from the inlet to the outlet with smooth, nearly linear contour lines and no spurious oscillations.

Conclusion

This work developed a mixed finite element method for the Brinkman model using the Taylor-Hood P_2 - P_1 element pair and backward Euler time discretization. The scheme was shown to be stable under the discrete inf-sup condition and convergent with optimal accuracy. Numerical experiments confirmed that the method accurately captures the velocity and pressure fields without spurious oscillations. Overall, the proposed approach provides a reliable and efficient framework for simulating Brinkman flow in porous media.

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1. Berdyshev, A. S., Baigereyev, D. R., & Boranbek, K. (2023). Numerical method for fractional-order generalization of the stochastic Stokes–Darcy model. *Mathematics*, 11, 3763. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math11173763>
2. Baishemirov, Zh. D., Berdyshev, A. S., Baigereyev, D. R., & Boranbek, K. (2024). Efficient numerical implementation of the time-fractional stochastic Stokes–Darcy model. *Fractal and Fractional*, 8, 476. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fractalfract8080476>
3. Brinkman, H. C. (1949). A calculation of the viscous force exerted by a flowing fluid on a dense swarm of particles. *Applied Scientific Research*, 1(1), 27–34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02120313>
4. Housiadas, K. D., & Tanner, R. I. (2020). The analytical solution of the Brinkman model for non-Brownian suspensions with Navier slip on the particles. *International Journal of Multiphase Flow*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2020.103298>
5. Boranbek, K., & Kazhymkan, A. (2026). Finite element method for the Brinkman model. In *First Congress of the Kazakhstan Mathematical Society: Abstracts Collection* (p. 522). Almaty: Institute of Mathematics and Mathematical Modeling.
6. Zhai, Q., Zhang, R., & Mu, L. (2016). A new weak Galerkin finite element scheme for the Brinkman model. *Communications in Computational Physics*, 19, 1409–1434. <https://doi.org/10.4208/cicp.scpde14.44s>
7. Hannukainen, A., Juntunen, M., & Stenberg, R. (2011). Computations with finite element methods for the Brinkman problem. *Computational Geosciences*, 15, 155–166. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10596-010-9204-4>
8. Sun, P., & Sun, Y. Asymptotic analysis and error estimates of mixed finite element method for the Brinkman model. *Journal of Scientific Computing*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10915-015-0131-3>
9. Jia, J., Lee, Y.-J., & Feng, Y. (2021). Hybridized weak Galerkin finite element methods for Brinkman equations. *Electronic Research Archive*, 29(3), 2489–2516. <https://doi.org/10.3934/era.2020126>